

Joint Blind Deconvolution and Image Correlography via a Bayesian Image Reconstruction Algorithm

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Abstract—Laser imaging through atmospheric turbulence is a challenging problem due primarily to turbulence close to the aperture. Amplitude measurements of the return beam in the plane of the aperture are immune to turbulence, but contain limited information about the Fourier phase of the target image. This paper suggests a method for using blind deconvolution of laser speckle degraded imagery together with correlography techniques in order to simplify the phase retrieval problem and produce coherent image reconstructions with spatial resolution not limited by the atmospheric conditions. The viability of the technique is demonstrated via computer simulation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

LADAR (LAsER Detection and Ranging) imaging systems are susceptible to the effects of atmospheric turbulence in much the same way incoherent imaging systems are; however, blind deconvolution methods [2] that are designed to mitigate the effects of turbulence by finding an optical transfer function for each frame of data are not applicable to LADAR imaging systems. This problem stems from the non-linearity in intensity of the coherent image formation process [1] and results in the fact that each frame of LADAR imagery cannot be described as the result of a convolution between the true scene intensity and an optical transfer function. One existing remedy for this problem involves averaging many frames of LADAR imagery in an effort to synthesize an incoherently formed image from many coherent ones. This technique capitalizes on the fact that the atmospheric effects will average to produce a blurring effect that is space-invariant and char-

acterized by an average optical transfer function. A blind deconvolution algorithm is then utilized to determine Fried's seeing parameter, which describes this transfer function, as well as the image of the scene [3]. This technique can produce diffraction-limited imagery if sufficiently many frames can be averaged and the diameter of the imaging system pupil is not excessively larger than the seeing parameter.

Another technique for recovering images of the scene involves a non-imaging technique known as correlography [4], [5], [6]. This technique involves collecting the intensity of the field in the pupil plane of the imaging system, which is related to the autocorrelation of the intensity of the scene. Because the pupil plane intensity is immune to turbulence near the aperture, atmospheric mitigation techniques are not required. Algorithms that recover the scene from its Fourier modulus or autocorrelation are known as phase retrieval algorithms. These algorithms can suffer from uniqueness problems, which allow erroneous solutions to be computed from the pupil plane data.

It is the goal of this research to use both image plane and pupil plane intensity data to derive a new image reconstruction algorithm that provides a solution more consistent with the true object intensity than imaging correlography methods alone and are less susceptible to atmospheric turbulence effects than blind deconvolution algorithms. Section 2 defines mathematical models describing how the image plane and pupil plane data sets are formed and their associated probability density functions. Section 3 outlines the derivation of the image reconstruction algorithm used to produce the results presented in Section 4. Section 5 serves to provide a summary of the work as well as conclusions drawn from it.

2. IMAGE AND PUPIL PLANE MODELS

The models describing both sets of data are derived in this section with the ultimate goal of providing probability density functions for the measurements in both planes. The models for the signals in the detector and pupil plane are derived for the time averaged case. The simulated data for each individual realization is generated by using field propagation models to compute the mean of the signal in each plane based on the intensity distribution of the object in the source plane. This

modeling strategy allows the algorithm to be tested on data that is not generated with a model that is completely consistent with that assumed in its statistical distribution.

Image Plane Data Model

The model for the average intensity in the focal plane capitalizes on the fact that a multi-frame average of laser speckle images converges to the distribution predicted by an incoherent image model [3]. This is due to the assumption that the phase at the target will be random and independent from observation to observation in much the same way that incoherent light produces a time varying phase distribution. The intensity distribution in the focal plane of the average image is then a convolution between the intensity of the source and a point spread function. This convolution is modeled discretely in order to facilitate the derivation of an algorithm in the computer to recover the image.

$$i(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N o(n, m)h(x - n, y - m; r_o),$$

where $o(n, m)$ is the object source intensity, $h(x, y; r_o)$ is the average point spread function of the imaging system, n, m, x, y are integers that denote sample indicies in both the object and source planes, N is the number of pixels on one side of a square source plane image and $i(x, y)$ is the average intensity in the image plane at the detector. In this case the point spread function is dominated by atmospheric turbulence close to the aperture of the imaging system. It is further assumed that because the signal to noise ratio in images that contain fully developed laser speckle is equal to one, that no attempt to remove interframe motion will be successful. With these assumptions, the average point spread function of the imaging system can be modeled as a combination of the average long exposure point spread function, parameterized by r_o (Frieds parameter), and a diffraction-limited point spread function [7]. The convolution model provides the mean of the probability density function (pdf) for the image plane data. The form of the pdf for an image averaged a large number of frames converges to the Poisson distribution [7].

$$P[D_i(x, y) = d_i(x, y)] = \frac{i(x, y)^{d_i(x, y)} e^{-i(x, y)}}{d_i(x, y)!},$$

where, $d_i(x, y)$ is the measured data in the image plane and $D_i(x, y)$ is the random variable representing the image plane data. Because the noise in each pixel is assumed to be statistically independent, the probability of realizing an entire average image is given by,

$$P[D = d; \forall(x, y) \in I_N] = \prod_{x=1}^N \prod_{y=1}^N \frac{i(x, y)^{d(x, y)} e^{-i(x, y)}}{d(x, y)!}, \quad (1)$$

where I_N represents the set of integers from one to N .

Pupil Plane Data Model

The pupil plane data model is based on one developed by Fienup and Idell [5], which relates the autocorrelation of the

source intensity distribution, R , to the average of the magnitude squared of the Fourier transform of the pupil plane field magnitude squared.

$$R(z, w) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N o(n, m)o(z + n, w + m). \quad (2)$$

$$D_r(z, w) = E[|\sum_{u=1}^N \sum_{v=1}^N F_a(u, v)e^{j2\pi(uz+vw)/N}|^2],$$

Where F_a is the field in the aperture plane of the LADAR imaging system and u, v, z, w are integer sample indicies in the pupil plane and source plane.

As suggested by this model, the pupil plane data will undergo a transformation and then it will be averaged to form an estimate of the autocorrelation. The pupil plane data, $D_a(u, v)$ possesses a Poisson distribution. Fourier transforming the data changes the pdf of the pupil plane data to some unknown form. Taking the magnitude squared further changes the distribution. In this research the appropriate distribution for the transformed pupil plane data is assumed to be Gaussian with a mean equal to $R(z, w)$ and a variance determined from a collection of observations. The transformed pupil plane data is computed from the aperture plane measurements via the following equation:

$$D_r(z, w) = \sum_{k=1}^K |\sum_{u=1}^N \sum_{v=1}^N D_{a_k}(u, v)e^{j2\pi(uz+vw)/N}|^2,$$

where D_r represents the transformed pupil plane data, K is the number of pupil plane images gathered and k is an integer indexing the frame number. The pdf of the transformed pupil plane data takes the following form:

$$P[D_r = d_r; \forall(z, w) \in I_N] = \prod_{z=1}^N \prod_{w=1}^N \frac{e^{-\frac{(d_r(z, w) - R(z, w))^2}{2\sigma^2}}}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}},$$

where σ^2 is the variance determined experimentally from the measured data.

Simulation Model

The models described in the previous subsections are used to derive the estimation algorithm in Section 3. The model discussed in this subsection is used to generate the synthetic data used in Section 4 to test the proposed reconstruction algorithm. Given the true scene $o(n, m)$. The field at the source for the k th observation, F_{o_k} , is simulated via the following equation:

$$F_{o_k}(n, m) = \sqrt{o(n, m)}e^{-j\phi_k(n, m)},$$

where ϕ_k is a uniformly distributed random variable at each pixel in the source field for each frame k . The field is propagated to the pupil plane via a Fraunhofer propagation. This

Fraunhofer propagation is simulated digitally via the Discrete Fourier Transform.

$$F_{a_k}(u, v) = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N F_{o_k}(n, m) e^{j2\pi(un+vm)/N}$$

The simulated data in the aperture plane, D_{a_k} , is synthesized by adding Poisson noise to the magnitude squared of the field in the aperture.

$$D_{a_k}(u, v) = |F_{a_k}(u, v)|^2 + n_k(u, v),$$

where $n_k(u, v)$ are the additive noise terms needed to give the data the appropriate statistics.

The simulated image plane data undergoes two more steps beyond those used to create the simulated pupil plane data. Taking the field in the aperture, the field in the detector is perturbed by atmospheric turbulence applied as a phase screen in the aperture of the imaging system. Phase screens with the appropriate Fried parameter are simulated [8] and are used to modify the field in the aperture. The field at the aperture is then propagated via another simulated Fraunhofer propagation to produce the field at the image plane, $F_{i_k}(x, y)$.

$$F_{i_k}(x, y) = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N F_{a_k}(u, v) e^{j\theta_k(u, v)} e^{j2\pi(ux+vy)/N},$$

where θ_k is the phase screen associated with data frame k . The image plane data D_{i_k} is equal to the magnitude squared of the field in the aperture plus noise, $N_k(x, y)$, that provides the image plane data with a Poisson distribution.

$$D_{i_k}(x, y) = |F_{i_k}(x, y)|^2 + N_k(x, y),$$

3. IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHM

The derivation of the joint blind image reconstruction algorithm begins with the formation of the joint pdf for both the pupil plane and image plane data.

$$P[D_r = d_r, D_i = d_i; \forall(z, w, x, y) \in I_n] = P[D_r = d_r; \forall(z, w) \in I_n] P[D_i = d_i; \forall(x, y) \in I_n]$$

The blind deconvolution algorithm developed by MacDonald [3] defines a prior for the Fried parameter.

$$f_{R_o} = e^{-r_o/r_{avg}}/r_{avg}, \quad (3)$$

The addition of the prior makes the joint estimation of the image and the seeing parameter a MAP estimation problem [9]. This can be accomplished by maximizing the joint pdf of the pupil plane and image plane data with respect to the object $o(n, m)$ given a choice for r_o . This process is repeated for different choices of r_o and r_{avg} over the range of possible seeing parameter values.

An iterative algorithm for estimating $o(n, m)$ is derived by maximizing the natural logarithm of the joint probability of

both sets of data.

$$L(o) = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N d_i(x, y) \ln(i(x, y)) - i(x, y) + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{-(d_r(z, w) - R(z, w))^2}{2\sigma^2}. \quad (4)$$

The derivative of the log-likelihood function with respect to the true scene at one point $o(n_o, m_o)$ is equal to [2], [6]:

$$\frac{\delta L(o)}{\delta o(n_o, m_o)} = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \frac{d_i(x, y) h(n_o, m_o; r_o)}{(i(x, y))} - 1 + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{(d_r(z, w) - R(z, w)) o(z + n_o, w + m_o)}{\sigma^2} + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{(d_r(z, w) - R(z, w)) o(n_o - z, m_o - w)}{\sigma^2}. \quad (5)$$

Setting the derivative equal to zero, collecting terms of the same sign yields,

$$1 + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{R(z, w) (o(z + n_o, w + m_o) + o(n_o - z, m_o - w))}{\sigma^2} = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \frac{d_i(x, y) h(n_o, m_o; r_o)}{(i(x, y))} + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{(d_r(z, w)) (o(z + n_o, w + m_o) + o(n_o - z, m_o - w))}{\sigma^2}. \quad (6)$$

Dividing both sides of equation (6) by the right side, multiplying both sides by $o(n_o, m_o)$ and defining the right side to be a function of old estimates and the left side to be the new estimate yields the following update equation for the scene.

$$o_{new}(n_o, m_o) = o^{old}(n_o, m_o) \times \left[\frac{\sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \frac{d_i(x, y) h(n_o, m_o; r_o)}{(i^{old}(x, y))}}{1 + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{R^{old}(z, w) (o^{old}(z + n_o, w + m_o) + o^{old}(n_o - z, m_o - w))}{\sigma^2}} + \frac{\sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{(d_r(z, w)) (o^{old}(z + n_o, w + m_o) + o^{old}(n_o - z, m_o - w))}{\sigma^2}}{1 + \sum_{z=1}^N \sum_{w=1}^N \frac{R^{old}(z, w) (o^{old}(z + n_o, w + m_o) + o^{old}(n_o - z, m_o - w))}{\sigma^2}} \right].$$

This algorithm runs for a fixed number of iterations before terminating for each value of r_o within the realm of possible choices. The Log-likelihood in equation (4) is computed and added to the natural logarithm of the prior for every possible value of r_{avg} to yield an expression proportional to the natural log of the *a posteriori* pdf. The MAP estimate for r_o is chosen to be the one where the *a posteriori* log-likelihood is maximized at the same value as r_{avg} . The image estimate that coincides with that choice of r_o and r_{avg} is the estimate of the true scene.

4. RESULTS

This section demonstrates the performance of the algorithm on real data. Figure 1 shows the original bar pattern used to generate the simulated image plane and pupil plane data. It is assumed that 1 million photons per observation are received from the target by both the pupil plane measurement system as well as the imaging system. Figure 2 shows a typical frame of image plane data taken with an aperture diameter of 20 centimeters and a seeing parameter of 7.5 centimeters. Figure 3 shows the average of 100 frames of atmospherically corrupted images of the bar target. Because the laser speckle noise is so dominant, attempts to align the images before averaging failed. The unregistered sum is used so that the average long-exposure optical transfer function can be used to deconvolve the image. Figure 4 shows the result of the blind deconvolution. The image produced by the algorithm failed to recover the bar pattern.

Figure 1. Bar pattern used as the coherent image source

Figure 2. A typical frame of image plane data.

Images of the pupil plane data are processed by the Fourier

Figure 3. An average of 100 frames of image plane data.

Figure 4. Blind deconvolution of the 100 frame average.

transform and then the magnitude squared of the result is taken. It was shown in Section 2 how this quantity is related to the autocorrelation of the original scene intensity. Figure 5 shows a typical frame that has undergone this process. Figure 6 shows the average of 100 frames of this data. Figure 7 demonstrates the results obtained from a phase retrieval algorithm [6]. Figure 8 shows the reconstruction obtained using the new algorithm. The bars are clearly more closely resemble the original bars used to generate the data. Figure 9 shows the Log-likelihood in equation (4) as a function of r_o for an $r_{avg} = 7.5$ cm, demonstrating that the correct seeing conditions were chosen by the algorithm.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Laser imaging through atmospheric turbulence with isoplanatic viewing conditions cannot be addressed through traditional blind deconvolution methods as convolution does not adequately describe the relationship between the true image

Figure 5. The magnitude squared of the Fourier transform of a typical frame of pupil plane data.

Figure 7. Result of applying a phase retrieval algorithm to 100 frame average of the magnitude squared of the Fourier transform of the pupil plane data.

Figure 6. A 100 frame average of the magnitude squared of the Fourier transform of the pupil plane data.

Figure 8. Result obtained from using the new algorithm that estimates the scene from both image plane and pupil plane data.

intensity and that measured in the focal plane of a LADAR imaging system. Convolution only describes this relationship adequately in the average and this averaging operation produces an optical transfer function that severely limits the resolution of the resulting image. This research has shown that where both blind deconvolution and image correlography methods fail, the new approach presented in this paper can exceed the performance of both by capitalizing on the strengths of each. Future research will focus on demonstrating the technique with measured image and pupil plane LADAR data. Research could also focus on quantifying the potential benefit of fusing these diverse types of data by computing bounds on imaging performance for the data sets individually as well as the fused data. Extending this work to anisoplanatic imaging scenarios is also of great interest as the isoplanatic assumption is very restrictive in its application to tactical imaging in

particular. Anisoplanatic viewing would add additional noise to the pupil plane data and may alter its relationship to the autocorrelation of the true scene. The blind deconvolution model has already been extended to the anisoplanatic case [3]. Further work must be done with pupil plane models to understand the effects of anisoplanatic viewing on the performance of phase retrieval algorithms as the phase effects of the intermediate path will not be eliminated when the magnitude squared of the field is captured by the detection system.

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Figure 9. Plot of the Log-Likelihood including the prior as a function of r_o for an $r_{avg} = 7.5$ cm.

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